

Is a Key Factor in Social and Psychological Rehabilitation of Disabled Children

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Abstract: The article of disabled children and disabled people in social-psychological rehabilitation has been the analysis of the phase. Psychological components of social rehabilitation rehabilitation of potential in the field of rehabilitation of persons with disabilities have a high chance of the task of operating characteristics and dynamic valuation of intellectual, mental activity regulate the level of enjoyment, disease and disability status and personal reactions proceeding from the position of the features is carried out.

Keywords: Of persons with disabilities, social and psychological rehabilitation, psychological to establish a diagnosis.

ACCESS

The rehabilitation of persons with disabilities-disabilities of personal, social, professional and other activities full or partial recovery of the ability to process on the organization of the system and developed a number of laws in the republic of uzbekistan. The rehabilitation of persons with disabilities-disabilities of personal, social, professional and other activities for the process of the formation of abilities to have the system and society is an important factor. This created shartsharoitlarva work chiqilganqonunlarnogironlarni make and social for adaptation, including the integration of society as full as possible to achieve financial independence and a cover to restrict or is directed.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Very recently, the problem of the social status of persons with disabilities to the attention of numerous local researchers (V.M. Astapov, O.I. Lebedinskaya, B.Yu.Shapiro, E.F. Achildieva, A.A. Baranov, R.K. Ignatieva, L.K. Grachev, TA Dobrovolskaya IP Katkova VV Kuznetsova, SS Kuchinskiy, SP Pyapkov GG Silaste, NB Shabalina, I. A. With Candles, S.P. Shevciuk Yu.G. Ellanskiy). Nevertheless, the analysis and the solution of this problem requires understanding still more. Research analysis and synthesis methods, including analysis covers the analysis of documents includes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following are the main directions of the rehabilitation of persons with disabilities and rehabilitation: medical rehabilitation, reconstructive surgery, prostheses and ortez, the resort treatment; referral to professional, vocational and general education, vocational education, employment and competition support (including special in the work place), adjust the production of social-ecological, social-pedagogical, socio-psychological and socio-cultural rehabilitation,

social compatibility; physical education and recreational activities, parts of the sports organization is an important issue.

Persons with disabilities (children with disabilities) or individual program or rehabilitation of persons with disabilities the rehabilitation and abilitation abilitatsiyasi individual software development, rehabilitation or handicapped children in public institutions for the implementation of the individual program given by abilitation medical-social examination forms and their “social rehabilitation measures” section in the following sections are provided: restore or abilitatsiya the social environment; social-psychological rehabilitation or abilitatsiya; socio-cultural rehabilitation or abilitatsiya; socio-household dastrulari compatibility among all them [1].

Local self-government bodies and organizations with the executive authorities of the procedure to ensure, regardless of their individual rehabilitation and abilitation of children with disabilities in state institutions or rehabilitation program or disabled individual to perform the activities entrusted to them by the program abilitation of information about their organizational-legal form of medical examinations and the social, social-psychological rehabilitation and abilitatsiya is provided in the following sections: social-psychological rehabilitation advice on psychological diagnostics; psychological adjustment; social-psychological training; persons with disabilities to social-psychological the patronage of the family of persons with disabilities. According to other sources, the disabled (disabled child) social-psychological rehabilitation and recovery – this mental activity of components (features high cognitive, emotional, and personal traits irodaviy) recovery (formation) service aimed at a set of means. To be added to the successful social adaptation of disabled people and the society in daily life, shaxslararo, socio-cultural and professional areas of life in the implementation of the activities [2].

M. DymochkaA.In E. MorozovV., E. JukovV. Methodological and psychological approaches to regulating the composition with disabilities in comprehensive rehabilitation rehabilitation recommendations are developed [3].

Psychological counseling include:

- for persons with disabilities is an important socio – psychological problems detection-shaxslararo relationships, communication, family, in the actions group (education, work), and society in different conflict situations in addressing the problems of personal growth, ijtimoiylashuv and others;
- nogironkishining (nogironbolaning) in their study to determine whether qilaoladimi to solve problems independently.
- open and mobilize internal resources to resolve them later, in order to discuss the problems identified those with disabilities; who identify social-psychological in addressing the problems, not enough in the restoration of social relationships and social-psychological rehabilitation in the formation of a positive attitude on basic psychological assistance;
- in the future the services necessary for social and psychological rehabilitation of the type (type) determination of the initial clarification of its content in each particular case.
- Pathology to the type of disability, the degree and type of life despite the restrictions of persons with disabilities (children with disabilities) social relations, social compatibility, and integration specialists can help you in solving problems in the field of ijtimoiylashuv.

In our opinion, the persons with disabilities (children with disabilities) for expert advice on issues-the lack of desire to ask for help from a psychologist to appeal the partial lack of persons with disabilities cannot be the basis for recommendations. In addition, normative-legal acts according to the rules of the disabled (children with disabilities) ip could have the character of recommendations. Personal experience with the disease depends on the treatment of the disease and the effects of new social to accept the status (disabled) can be delayed and qualified psychological help to those in need. It should be noted that, or substantially clear violation

mental function, to limit the level of control over their actions 2 and 3 respectively to bring the task of narrowing can be primarily psychological counseling and psychotherapeutic and psychological help fix. There are the following types of counseling: psychological-pedagogical, family, personal, young professional. You can combine this type of professionals in the practice of psychology [4].

Depending on the specific task of psychological diagnosis, using experimental methods, including persons with disabilities (children with disabilities) cases taking into account the need for further evaluation of the dynamics of the environment, or a pathological condition associated with the change in the conditions of persons with disabilities (children with disabilities), which hinder the development of the combination of the assessment of personal property, taking the structure and assessment of the level of disorder of mental activity is carried out.

The purpose of psychological diagnostics psychological rehabilitation (abilitatsiya) development of the work program (if required) and rehabilitation (abilitatsiya) the effectiveness of assessment (assessment of the state dynamics) [5].

Psychological diagnostics includes the following steps:

- 1) the initial analysis of documents on the subject (medical and social);
- 2) clarification of the goals and objectives of the planning of psixodiagnostik technique and its programs;
- 3) chat;
- 4) psychological rehabilitation-expert diagnosis;
- 5) data processing and analysis psixodiagnostik;
- 6) preparation of conclusions on the results in psixodiagnostik;
- 7) the components of the individual program of rehabilitation of persons with disabilities in the development of psychological, social-psychological rehabilitation services, clarification of the content and direction [6].

Psychological components of social rehabilitation rehabilitation of potential in the field of rehabilitation of persons with disabilities have a high chance of the task of operating characteristics and dynamic valuation of intellectual, mental activity regulate the level of enjoyment, disease and disability status and personal reactions proceeding from the position of the features is carried out.

Social-psychological diagnosis private, but one of the very important functions for the early detection of the incidence of depression and suicide risk is detected. Psychological chronic pain syndrome in the diagnostic process, insulation, family separation, a sense of frustration and actions are given particular attention to other risk factors for suicide.

Medical social psychological adjustment is necessary to normalize your high holativa biomaydonini different stress levels. The intent of psychological adjustment-available anatom negative change moves the maximum break in cover is to prevent and cognitive processes [7].

Depending on the degree of correction approaches different break structure and, in particular, pathological and neyropsikologik methods can be applied. Always psychological correction persons with disabilities (children with disabilities) and is not limited to this process may include working with all the social environment.

Symptomatic psychological correction (development anormallik on signs) and to eliminate the causes (anormallik to eliminate the source of development) can be. Psychological correction of the activity of sensory-emotional activity and anatomical, emotional sphere, the conduct, the person may be directed to.

The purpose of psychological correction of the condition of the optimization social development, the development of some aspects of the chamber's activities, psychological neoplazmalarni may be associated with the formation of [8].

Social-psychological training-this psixotravmatik of the situation, aimed at elimination of the consequences of the anatomical neyropshik from disabled to active psychological effects, disease, wounds, injuries due to environment or social conditions have weakened, but the new social conditions needed for successful adaptation, aimed at allowing them to successfully fulfill different social roles the form of professional, social and others) and social relationships and can be added to various fields of life really.

Social-psychological training of persons with disabilities within the framework of experience working with active psychological training (as a result of psychological, communicative competence increase), many of your new-strategies for the formation of [9].

Available from pathology in the form of psychological training of working age and form a group, no matter disabilities (children with disabilities) can be an effective means of giving help. Psychological training of social-psychological rehabilitation and disabled people (disabled children) abilitatsiya along with other forms of pain, and the position of "disabled" 's new social status and / or personal and social skills, skills, improving social activity and h. k.

Preventive psychological –psychological knowledge in this social-psychological skills and increase their social-psychological content of the problem on the need to use this knowledge to work on themselves (motivation) for the purchase of the formation of persons with disabilities (children with disabilities) as well as helping to create conditions for the activities of persons with disabilities full spiritual (or eliminate family, work, and other social groups of persons with disabilities that are included to reduce anxiety, psychological factors), first of all, social relations [10].

Social-psychological in the family visiting disabled people, in the production of the problems of adaptation in the society in general the incidence of mental discomfort associated with the timely detection is to check it regularly.psychological assistance [11,12].

Social-psychological rehabilitation, including cognitive, emotional, means the correction of the system is carried out using special equipment. Thus, the touch-room, the anatomical method of feedback, computerized system using the technique cogniplus and other emotional-cognitive methods of the correction.

Disabilities (children with disabilities) psychological reactions to specific contours and specific feature of the disease is personal to him much assistance, as well as its high be associated with the move. Rehabilitation measures are defined and their work does not have clearly defined borders that lay in a different combination of psychology you can use the method in [13-15].

The type of pathological process and the function of the body disorder of a particular type of social-psychological rehabilitation determines the direction of the implementation of the social-psychological rehabilitation of choosing the appropriate method or abilitatsiyani defines the overall direction, but the social-psychological rehabilitation process aniqlamaydi. This pathological conditions, the same level of impairment of the function of the body, leading specialist of psychology due to the composition of the rehabilitation methods used by disabled (handicapped children) psychologist and specialist (various schools using the technique of psychological) of individual preferences-including personal characteristics can vary. Social-psychological rehabilitation of violation of certain pathological processes and functional studies among the methods is typical, and this is mainly associated with the specific features of the defect structure is not specific pathological processes, but its consequences, in particular, the disabled person's (children with disabilities) disease.

SUMMARY

Social rehabilitation of the disabled or abilitatsiya medical rehabilitation, vocational rehabilitation, psychological-pedagogical rehabilitation and anatomical physical education, sport is carried out in close collaboration with. In practice primary basic principle of the program or the concluding abilitatsiya internal psychological psychological rehabilitation, second and third level defects and saved the directions of mental activity, as well as taking reabilitantning is to consider the content of the omission of personal characteristics. Later, people with a disability (disabled children) in various pathological conditions abilitatsiya some differences in rehabilitation and we will dwell briefly about this in our opinion, children with disabilities (children with disabilities) may be important in the formation of ip. Social-psychological rehabilitation to men who have children with disabilities or functional diseases in some pathological processes abilitatsiya and I will yoda from the spiritual side.

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